

A note on estimating micronutrient reference values from nonlinear intake-response data using **R** – vitamin D as example

Version 1

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Introduction

Micronutrient reference values may be used to ensure that the requirements are met for the majority of the individuals in a certain target population. Estimation of reference values requires intake-response data, where intake is the exposure and serum level in the blood the resulting response. As intake will vary between individuals, it is natural to view modelling of intake-response data as a special case of dose-response analysis. Once the intake-response curve has been fitted, inverse regression may be used to estimate intake levels that ensure that certain targeted micronutrients levels (measured in blood samples) are achieved with a certain probability.

For vitamin D, intake-response data should follow an increasing s-shaped curve for the 25(OH)D concentration (nmol/L) as a function of vitamin D intake ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) (Heaney, 2012). In practice there are often limitations in the range of intake values observed in studies, prohibiting observing the entire s-shaped curve. Both linear regression models with and without transformations of intakes and/or concentrations have been used in the past: Cashman *et al.* (2011) used simple linear regression with untransformed intakes and concentrations; Cashman *et al.* (2017) used linear regression with logarithm-transformed intakes and concentrations whereas Cashman *et al.* (2021) used linear regression with square root-transformed concentrations and untransformed intakes. These linear regression models may be viewed as ad hoc approximations of an s-shaped curve within a limited range of intakes. However, nonlinear regression models have also been used in a few studies, but the involved statistical modelling approach was only very briefly described (Mortensen *et al.*, 2016; Smith *et al.*, 2016). Also, no software script was made available.

Therefore, the aim of this note is to explain the statistical methodology in more detail and, in particular, to show how to use the statistical environment **R** (R Core Team, 2020), for estimating micronutrient reference values with confidence intervals based on nonlinear regression models. The note is self-contained as it contains all data and all **R** code used.

Methods

S-shaped model

Often, it may be assumed that concentrations follow normal distributions with means that depend on intakes through an s-shaped intake-response curve (and standard deviations that does not depend on the intake, i.e., they are constant). In this note, we will consider the asymptotic regression model, which is a special case of the s-shaped, four-parameter Weibull type 2 model (Ritz *et al.*, 2019). It should be noted that alternative s-shaped models are also available, including the commonly used log-logistic model and the Weibull type 1 models.

The three-parameter asymptotic regression model function f , describing mean 25(OH)D concentrations as a function of the intake x , may be written as follows:

$$f(x) = c + (d - c)(1 - \exp(-x/e))$$

where the parameter c is the lower limit on the 25(OH)D concentration (corresponding to an intake equal to 0, that is $x=0$), the parameter d is the physiological upper limit on the 25(OH)D concentration, and the positive parameter e is determining the steepness of the increase in 25(OH)D concentration as the intake (x) increases: the larger the more steep is the increase. The three parameters c , d , and e may be estimated by means of nonlinear least squares (Ritz *et al.*, 2019).

Inverse regression

Once the estimated intake-response curve and the corresponding (marginal) prediction intervals have been obtained (see Huet *et al.* (2004) for details on prediction intervals), inverse regression may be used for conversion from the concentration scale back to the intake scale. Specifically, certain concentrations levels are chosen: For vitamin D it could be the following 25OH(D) concentrations: 25, 30, or 50 nmol/L. Additionally, for each concentration it needs to be decided on the lower limit of the prediction interval: which certainty is targeted? For instance, choosing the lower limit of a 95% prediction interval for the 25 nmol/L concentration implies estimating the intake level that ensures a serum 25OH(D) concentration of at least 25 nmol/L for 97.5% of the population on average. In practice, 50%, 80%, 90%, and 95% prediction intervals have been used (e.g., Cashman *et al.*, 2021).

In principle, it would be possible and tractable to invert the above equation mathematically to obtain an explicit closed-form solution. However, in practice, also in view of capabilities in statistical software, it seems much more efficient to use numerical approaches for solving equations. One such numerical approach is the bisection method, which is a simple, robust, and fast method for one-dimensional problems.

To obtain 95% confidence interval for these intake levels estimated through inverse regression, a bootstrap approach seems to be the most convenient choice as it allows incorporates the uncertainty in the estimated intake-response regression curve as well as in the estimated prediction intervals. Alternatively, it might be possible to apply the delta method but it requires the formula for the inverse regression as well as an estimated variance-covariance for all involved parameter estimates, including for the residual standard error. In this note, a parametric bootstrap approach was used where the nonlinear regression model was fitted repeatedly to permuted datasets (Davison & Hinkley, 1997).

Defining bootstrap functions

Two **R** helper functions are defined: `bootFctRefVal()` and `bootFct()`.

The function `bootFctRefVal()` is used for defining the specific input needed for the `bootFct()`, for doing inverse regression based on nonlinear regression using the model fitting function `drm()` and its prediction method, both available in the package *drc* (Ritz *et al.*, 2019). The bisection method is applied through the **R** function `uniroot()`, which, by default, is restricted to the intake interval [0.001, 1000]. Specifically, the function `bootFctRefVal()` takes as input the original dataset (containing intake values in the first column and concentrations in the second column; the order is important), the cut-off concentrations and coverage percentages (with sensible default choices), a seed to initiate the random number generator used for generating bootstrap samples (in the function `bootFct()`), and additionally two argument for fine-tuning the bisection method (again with a sensible default) and specifying the number of bootstrap samples to use (999 is the default). The three-parameter asymptotic regression model is specified through the argument `fct = AR.3()` in the model fitting function `drm()`.

```
bootFctRefVal <- function(dataF, cutoffs = c(25, 30, 40, 50),
  probs = c(0.5, 0.9, 0.95, 0.975), intakeInt = c(0.001, 1000), Rval = 999, seedVal)
{
  nonlinFit <- drm(dataF[, c(2, 1)], fct = AR.3(), na.action = na.omit)

  nonlin.data <- data.frame(intake = dataF[complete.cases(dataF[, 1:2]), 1],
    fit = fitted(nonlinFit), resid = residuals(nonlinFit))

  nonlin.fun <- function(dat, inds, cutoff, percval)
```

```

{
  nonlinFit.boot <- drm(fit+resid[inds] ~ intake, data = dat, fct = AR.3(),
                      start = coef(nonlinFit), na.action = na.omit)

  predFct <- function(x)
  {
    predMat <- predict(nonlinFit.boot, data.frame(x), se.fit = TRUE)
    cutoff = predMat[["Prediction"]] + qnorm(percval) * sqrt(predMat[["SE"]]^2 +
                  summary(nonlinFit.boot)[["resVar"]])
  }
  uniRes <- try(uniroot(predFct, interval = intakeInt), silent = TRUE)

  if (!inherits(uniRes, "try-error")) {rootVal <- uniRes[["root"]]} else {
    rootVal <- NA}

  return(rootVal)
}
lencu <- length(cutoffs)
lenpr <- length(probs)

set.seed(seedVal)
bootFct(nonlin.data, nonlin.fun, rep(cutoffs,
  rep(lenpr, lencu)), rep(probs, lencu), Rval)
}

```

The function `bootFct()`, which is called from `bootFctRefVal()`, is the function that is doing the actual bootstrapping, utilizing the functions `boot()` and `boot.ci()` from the package *boot*. Specifically, this function takes as input the original dataset, augmented with additional columns containing fitted values and residuals for the original model fit and possibly reduced through omission of row containing missing values, a function that carries out model fitting (based on a permuted dataset) and returns parameter estimates of interest (the reference values) and, finally, two arguments `cVec` and `pVec` that specifies the chosen cut-off concentration and coverage percentage (for the prediction interval). By default, the function `bootFct()` runs 999 bootstrap samples repeatedly in a loop for each specified combination of cut-off concentrations and coverage percentages. The resulting output contains mean, standard deviation and 95% confidence intervals based on the normal approximation and based on percentiles, respectively, obtained using the bootstrapped estimates. Additionally, the number of bootstrap samples where the model fitting or bisection method failed is reported as well as mean and standard deviation for the logarithm-transformed bootstrapped estimates, which could be useful in case the distribution of estimated reference values would be right-skewed.

```

bootFct <- function(nonlin.data, nonlin.fun, cVec, pVec, Rval)
{
  lVec <- length(cVec)
  resMatrix <- matrix(NA, lVec, 2 + 4 + 4 + 2)
  for (i in 1:lVec)
  {
    bootRes <- boot(nonlin.data, nonlin.fun, R = Rval,
                  cutoff = cVec[i], percval = pVec[i])
    bootciRes <- try(boot.ci(bootRes, type = c("norm", "perc")), silent = TRUE)

    if (inherits(bootciRes, "try-error")) {bootCI <- rep(NA, 4)} else {bootCI <-
      c(bootciRes[["normal"]][2:3], bootciRes[["percent"]][4:5])}

    resMatrix[i, ] <- c(cVec[i], pVec[i], bootRes[["t0"]],
                    mean(bootRes[["t"]], na.rm = TRUE),

```

```

        sd(bootRes[["t"]], na.rm = TRUE),
        sum(is.na(bootRes[["t"]])),
        bootCI,
        log(bootRes[["t0"]]),
        sd(log(bootRes[["t"]]), na.rm = TRUE))
    }
    colnames(resMatrix) <- c("Conc", "Perc", "Intake", "Intakeb", "SE", "NoNA",
        "nCI.Lo", "nCI.Hi", "pCI.Lo", "pCI.Hi", "IntLog", "SELog")
    resMatrix
}

```

Artificial data are generated using the model fit reported by Mortensen *et al.* (2016):

```

intakeVal <- runif (110, 0, 30)
concVal <- 23.9 + (89.8 - 23.9) * (1 - exp(-intakeVal / 15.7)) + rnorm(110, 0, 10)
simData <- data.frame(intake = intakeVal, conc = concVal)

```

Note that the results reported by Mortensen *et al.* (2016) were obtained using data from 4-8-year old children.

Results

The artificial data are shown below using the *ggplot2* graphical system in **R**. The nonlinear increasing trend in the intake-response data towards a horizontal plateau is discernible. This observation justifies fitting a nonlinear regression model below.

```

library(ggplot2)

p1 <- ggplot(simData, aes(x = intake, y = conc)) +
  geom_point(alpha = 0.5, show.legend = FALSE) + theme_bw() +
  xlab(expression(paste("Total vitamin D intake (", mu, "g/day)"))) +
  ylab("Serum 25(OH)D (nmol/L)") +
  scale_x_continuous(limits = c(0, 30)) +
  scale_y_continuous(limits = c(0, 110))

p1

```


For concentrations 25, 30, 40, and 50 nmol/L and 50%, 90%, 95%, and 97.5% certainty (the default choices), the following estimated reference values and corresponding 95% (percentile) confidence intervals were obtained:

```
library(boot)
library(drc)
refValues <- bootFctRefVal(simData, seedVal = 202203211)
refValues[, -c(7, 8, 11, 12)]
```

##	Conc	Perc	Intake	Intakeb	SE	NoNA	pCI.Lo	pCI.Hi
## [1,]	25	0.500	NA	0.3679008	0.2751266	717	0.006242257	0.9726081
## [2,]	25	0.900	2.9388538	2.8257254	0.5265630	0	1.686439568	3.7513814
## [3,]	25	0.950	3.9783466	3.8803219	0.5417810	0	2.766267973	4.9273076
## [4,]	25	0.975	4.9374284	4.8361060	0.5665910	2	3.750341376	5.9570305
## [5,]	30	0.500	0.9519163	1.0061096	0.5077812	83	0.088311943	1.9623907
## [6,]	30	0.900	4.4959079	4.4322305	0.5089603	1	3.442146129	5.4149546
## [7,]	30	0.950	5.6464461	5.5541505	0.5642202	3	4.464280294	6.6990313
## [8,]	30	0.975	6.7150326	6.5906904	0.6077512	1	5.422707930	7.7965227
## [9,]	40	0.500	3.8619180	3.8410171	0.4635833	0	2.871545121	4.7126675
## [10,]	40	0.900	8.1538295	8.0700511	0.6214161	2	6.908863768	9.3464616
## [11,]	40	0.950	9.5998460	9.5157077	0.7072679	2	8.156233985	10.9807006
## [12,]	40	0.975	10.9601723	10.8410367	0.8300938	3	9.200012992	12.5346203
## [13,]	50	0.500	7.3723027	7.3659346	0.5107902	0	6.412835352	8.4403629
## [14,]	50	0.900	12.8176716	12.7368923	0.8197641	0	11.138943368	14.2477471
## [15,]	50	0.950	14.7308040	14.5884677	0.9142477	3	12.817112522	16.3730716
## [16,]	50	0.975	16.5767560	16.4918890	1.0305248	10	14.465571295	18.5264463

For instance, to ensure that 50% of the population reaches 40 nmol/L the required intake is 3.86 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ with a corresponding 95% confidence interval [2.87, 4.71] $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$. To ensure that 97.5% of the population reaches

40 nmol/L the required intake is 10.96 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ with a corresponding 95% confidence interval [9.20, 12.53] $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$.

Again, *ggplot2* may be used for plotting the fitted intake-response curve along with the accompanying (marginal) 50%, 80%, 90%, and 95% prediction intervals (which may be used for estimating reference intake values ensuring concentrations above 40 nmol/L with 50%, 90%, 95%, and 97.5% certainty). Initially, predicted values used in the plot are obtained using the 'predict method in *drc*:

```
intakeValGrid <- seq(0, 30, by = 0.1)

predictions1 <- as.data.frame(cbind(Intake = intakeValGrid,
  predict(modelFit, data.frame(intake = intakeValGrid), interval = "prediction",
  level = 0.95)))
predictions2 <- as.data.frame(cbind(Intake = intakeValGrid,
  predict(modelFit, data.frame(intake = intakeValGrid), interval = "prediction",
  level = 0.90)))
predictions3 <- as.data.frame(cbind(Intake = intakeValGrid,
  predict(modelFit, data.frame(intake = intakeValGrid), interval = "prediction",
  level = 0.80)))
```

Then the fitted intake-response and the corresponding prediction intervals are shown below:

```
p1 <- p1 +
  geom_line(data = predictions1, aes(x = Intake, y = Prediction),
    alpha = 0.5, show.legend = FALSE) +
  geom_ribbon(data = predictions1, aes(x = Intake, y = Prediction, ymin = Lower,
    ymax = Upper),
    alpha = 0.3, show.legend = FALSE) +
  geom_ribbon(data = predictions2, aes(x = Intake, y = Prediction, ymin = Lower,
    ymax = Upper),
    alpha = 0.4, show.legend = FALSE) +
  geom_ribbon(data = predictions3, aes(x = Intake, y = Prediction, ymin = Lower,
    ymax = Upper),
    alpha = 0.5, show.legend = FALSE) +
  geom_segment(aes(x = 0, y = 40, xend = 30, yend = 40), lty = 2) +
  geom_segment(aes(x = refValues[12, 3], y = 40, xend = refValues[12, 3], yend = 0),
    lty = 2) +
  geom_segment(aes(x = refValues[11, 3], y = 40, xend = refValues[11, 3], yend = 7.3),
    lty = 2) +
  geom_segment(aes(x = refValues[10, 3], y = 40, xend = refValues[10, 3], yend = 0),
    lty = 2) +
  geom_segment(aes(x = refValues[9, 3], y = 40, xend = refValues[9, 3], yend = 0),
    lty = 2) +
  geom_text(aes(x = 20, y = 43), label = "Cut-off: 40 nmol/L") +
  geom_text(aes(x = refValues[12, 3] + 1.6, y = 5), label = "97.5%") +
  geom_text(aes(x = refValues[11, 3], y = 5), label = "95%") +
  geom_text(aes(x = refValues[10, 3] - 1, y = 5), label = "90%") +
  geom_text(aes(x = refValues[9, 3] - 1, y = 5), label = "50%")
p2
```


The dashed line segments in the figure shows how requiring higher certainty to reach 40 nmol/L implies higher reference values.

Discussion

In view of the available, flexible, and robust software for fitting nonlinear s-shaped curves, it would seem natural that nonlinear regression would become the preferred modelling approach for establishing reference values. The **R** code described in this note is easily modified to accommodate 1) other micronutrients than vitamin D and 2) other types of s-shaped nonlinear regression models such as the log-logistic model (Ritz *et al.*, 2019).

Nonlinear regression remains more challenging than linear regression, in particular for intake-response data that show very little curvature. In such cases linear regression would suffice for describing the intake-response curve and inverse regression using prediction intervals could still be used. Another disadvantage of using nonlinear regression modelling is that it becomes more difficult to incorporate covariate adjustments as compared to linear regression models.

In this note prediction intervals were used, but one apparent extension would be to use tolerance intervals instead of prediction intervals: A 95% prediction interval will contain 95% of future observations on average. In contrast, a tolerance interval will contain at least 95% of future observations with 95% confidence (or any other prespecified confidence level). By definition the tolerance interval is wider than the corresponding prediction interval. However, with increasing sample size prediction and tolerance intervals will become more and more similar as both approach covering the middle 95% of the population.

In case data would be available for several studies (and not just one as assumed in this note), simultaneous modelling of several intake-response curves should be considered. One approach would be to use nonlinear mixed-effects models, which have been used successfully for other types of dose-response data (Baty *et al.*, 2016).

Finally, it should be mentioned that benchmark dose analysis is a related methodology that also involves dose-response analysis followed by inverse regression to establish certain reference values but these values are based on confidence intervals and not prediction intervals as is the case for determining micronutrient reference values.

References

- Baty, F., Ritz, C., van Gestel, A., Brutsche, M., Gerhard, D. (2016). Modeling the oxygen uptake kinetics during exercise testing of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases using nonlinear mixed models. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, **16**, 66. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-016-0173-8>
- Cashman, K. D., FitzGerald, A. P., Viljakainen, H. T., Jakobsen, J., Michaelsen, K. F., Lamberg-Allardt, C., Mølgaard, C. (2011). Estimation of the dietary requirement for vitamin D in healthy adolescent white girls. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, **93**, 549-55. <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.110.006577>
- Cashman, K. D., Ritz, C., Kiely, M., Odin Collaborators. (2017). Improved Dietary Guidelines for Vitamin D: Application of Individual Participant Data (IPD)-Level Meta-Regression Analyses. *Nutrients*. **9**, 469. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu9050469>
- Cashman, K. D., Kiely, M. E., Andersen, R., Grønborg, I. M., Madsen, K. H., Nissen, J., Tetens, I., Tripkovic, L., Lanham-New, S. A., Toxqui, L., Vaquero, M. P., Trautvetter, U., Jahreis, G., Mistry, V. V., Specker, B. L., Hower, J., Knoll, A., Wagner, D., Vieth, R., Öhlund, I., Åkeson, P. K., Brett, N. R., Weiler, H. A., Ritz, C. (2021). Individual participant data (IPD)-level meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials with vitamin D-fortified foods to estimate Dietary Reference Values for vitamin D. *European Journal of Nutrition*, **60**, 939-959. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00394-020-02298-x>
- Davison, A. C. & Hinkley, D. V. (1997). *Bootstrap Methods and Their Applications*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Heaney, R. P. (2012). Vitamin D - baseline status and effective dose. *New England Journal of Medicine*, **367**, 77-78. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMe1206858>
- Huet, S., Bouvier, A., Poursat, M.-A., Jolivet, E. (2004). *Statistical Tools for Nonlinear Regression: A Practical Guide with S-PLUS and R Examples*. Second edition. Springer, New York.
- Mortensen, C., Damsgaard, C. T., Hauger, H., Ritz, C., Lanham-New, S. A., Smith, T. J., Hennessy, Á., Dowling, K., Cashman, K. D., Kiely, M., Mølgaard, C. (2016). Estimation of the dietary requirement for vitamin D in white children aged 4-8 y: a randomized, controlled, dose-response trial. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, **104**, 1310-1317. <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.116.136697>
- R Core Team (2020). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Ritz, C., Jensen, S. M., Gerhard, D., Streibig, J. C. (2019). *Dose-Response Analysis Using R*. CRC Press, Boca Raton. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b21966>
- Smith, T. J., Tripkovic, L., Damsgaard, C. T., Mølgaard, C., Ritz, C., Wilson-Barnes, S. L., Dowling, K. G., Hennessy, A., Cashman, K. D., Kiely, M., Lanham-New, S. A., Hart, K. H. (2016). Estimation of the dietary requirement for vitamin D in adolescents aged 14-18 years: a dose-response, double-blind, randomized placebo-controlled trial. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, **104**, 1301-1309. <https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.116.138065>